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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOMATOTYPE CHARACTERISTICS AND RESTING ENERGY EXPENDITURE

Isidora Semnic¹, Danijel Slavić², David Ivanov², Andrea Zubnar², Dea Karaba Jakovljević², Nada Naumović²

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

908001d21@mf.uns.ac.rs

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Physiology, Novi Sad, Serbia

danijel.slavic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction: It is well known that body composition, primarily fat-free mass, is a major determinant of resting energy expenditure (REE), which actually accounts for most of total daily energy expenditure. A higher rate of energy expenditure is associated with more desirable metabolic and physiological profile of an individual. The aim of this study was to examine the association between different parameters of body composition, primarily the individual components of somatypes and the resting energy expenditure.

Materials and methods: The study involved 48 young (20.46 ± 0.9 years) subjects of both gender (24 females and 24 males) with an average BMI 23.61 ± 2.73 kg/m² and fat mass percentage $18.77 \pm 8.6\%$. Anthropometric and measurements of REE were assessed. Somatypes were determined using the Heath and Carter method. The relative indices of REE were expressed in kcal/24h/kg indicating the rate of metabolic consumption during rest. Pearson's r was used to estimate the level of correlation.

Results: Males had endomorphic mesomorph (3.1-5.2-2.4) and females mesomorphic endomorph (4.6-3.9-2.4) somatotype. Absolute values of REE were positively correlated with body height, fat free mass, muscle mass, body surface area and weight ($p < 0.001$), while fat percentage was negatively correlated with REE ($-0.396, p < 0.01$). While the relative indices of REE were negatively correlated with endomorphic and mesomorphic component of somatypes ($-0.361, p < 0.05$ and $-0.444, p < 0.01$), they were significantly positively correlated with ectomorphic component ($0.544, p < 0.001$).

Table. Correlation between anthropometric parameters and resting energy expenditure.

	REE	REE/TM
TV	0.656 ***	-0.122
TM	0.540 ***	-0.477 ***
BMI	0.199	-0.604 ***
BSA	0.617 ***	-0.377 **
WHR	0.329 *	-0.144
WHtR	0.082	-0.488 ***
SUM 7	-0.241	-0.461 ***
FAT %	-0.396 **	-0.287 *
FFM	0.645 ***	-0.236
MUSCLE %	0.334 *	0.299 *
MUSCLE kg	0.625 ***	-0.181
ENDOMORPHY	-0.307 *	-0.361 *
MESOMORPHY	0.264	-0.444 **
ECTOMORPHY	0.100	0.544 ***

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Conclusion: A more pronounced ectomorphic component of somatotype is associated with higher rate of resting energy expenditure and leads to a more desirable health and physiological profile of an individual.

Keywords: basal metabolism, anthropometry, somatotypes, body composition, body image.